

Educational values of Akwantukese festival celebration

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Abstract

The study which is aimed at drawing attention to the educational values of *Akwantukese* festival celebration adopted the qualitative research approach. Due to the nature of the study, purposive sampling technique was employed. Interviews and observations were the main instruments used for the data collection. Results showed that, virtue, humility, unity, love and respect are embedded in the *Akwantukese* festival and are exhibited, sustained and transferred from generation to generation through the celebration. It is highly recommended that the chiefs and the people of New Juaben should try as much as possible to telecast the festival celebration on the national television for the whole nation to observe and learn the educational values it exhibit. The chiefs should also try as much as possible to celebrate the festival every year since it educates the general public socially, psychologically and artistically.

Keywords:

Educational Values, *Akwantukese* Festival, Customs, Culture, Traditions, Festival Celebration

1.0 Introduction

Educational values according to Lovat and Hawkes (2013) are the activities that are good, useful and important to the wellbeing of people. They further established that educational values have the opportunity to mould the character of the people in order to make them better person in the society. Educational values are the importance people place on their principles or beliefs and how they shall be treasured and pass it on the younger generations (Hill,2004). The educational values are not just mere teaching but it is how to change a person's behaviour permanently for him or her to be accepted by all in the society.

Festivals celebration are special occasions for learning customs, traditions, values and expected code of ethics of a society as well as other good things that one observes during the event (Lee, Arcodia and Jeonglyeol, 2012). In the course of the *Akwantukese* festival celebration, people who do not know the norms and culture of the society directly or indirectly learn from the various activities that go on. Again, foreigners who do not know the cultural and social norms also learn them. Aisah (2015) maintains that educational values in festival celebration teach and develop values such as love, unity, respect and humility into people. Dedume (2011) is of the view that through education values, norms and ideologies of a society is transmitted to its people especially the young ones.

Moreover, one major force or element that brings people from all walks of life together is festival celebration which *Akwantukese* festival is of no exception, and through this activity the way of life of the people are exhibited and learnt by people across the globe (Wuleka Kuuder et al., 2012). Ojo-Ade (1989) also added that festival celebration is a way of life fashioned by a people in their collective endeavour. *Akwantukese* festival celebration is the sum total of the people's systems such beliefs, arts and rituals which must be instilled into the members of the community in order to preserve and sustain their precious culture and traditions.

In spite of all these educational values deeply rooted in the *Akwantukese* festival celebration, the emergence of colonialism, westernization and other events that accompany the industrial revolution has swept some significant aspects of the people's cultural heritage replacing it with global cultural trends of modernization (Giddens, 2000), particularly in the sphere of the festival celebration. Yet the depletion and extinction of these cultural practices rooted in the festival celebration, as they were known positively to promote the norms of the people prior to the era of colonialism have not been given much attention especially in the sphere of the *Akwantukese* traditional festival. In view of these, this study sorts to educate people on the significant contribution of the educational values embedded in the *Akwantukese* festival celebration. This will help to sustain and bring back the formal values the festival was contributing to the members of the society.

1.1 History of the *Akwantukese* Festival

The *Akwantukese* festival which is celebrated by the New Juaben comprises of the eight towns: Asokore, Effiduase, Oyoko, Jumapo, Suhyen, Akwadum, Ada and Koforidua in the Eastern

Region of Ghana) was established as a result of two civil wars which were fought within forty-three years (1832 and 1875) between Kumasi and Asante Dwaben. These two towns were the two most affluent states in the Asante Union (Attobrah,1976). These wars led to the momentous evacuation of the Dwaben people and their allies- Asokore, Oyoko and Effiduase to the then British Protectorate in the Eastern Region and subsequently created the New Juaben State in 1878.

Asante Dwaben which led the voyage, was an established State for almost two centuries prior to the establishment of the Asante Union under their leaders Adarkwa Yiadom (1670-1715) and Osei Hwedie (1715-1730). According to Attobrah (1976) the Dwaben State grew and became one of the leading and most powerful Asante States in the area and it was one of the five established states that joined in a coalition to form the Asante Union.

The Asante Dwaben state was part of the confederacy and went for many wars. The wars were won due to their courage, strength and agility. For this reason, they were referred to as *oyoko manu* meaning the second most powerful state after Kumasi. Some of the wars that the Dwaben went were the battle at Feyiase (1699-1791), the Asante-Gyaman war (1799-1818) where the Gyamanhene Kwadwo Adinkra was killed and the battle of Nsamanko and Akatamanso wars in 1824 and 1826 where the then Governor of the Gold Coast Sir Charles McCarthy was beheaded (Osei,2004).

Attobrah (1976) adds that the war between Asante and Denkyira was generated by the Dwabenhene Nana Adarkwa Yiadom due to the extreme demands of Ntim Gyakari and through the war, the Dwabenhene who led the war killed Ntim Gyakari the Chief of Denkyira at the battle of Feyiase and decapitated him.

The Dwabenhene, Adarkwa Yiadom who killed the Denkyirahene sent his head to the Asantehene as a sign of victory for the Asante. The Asantes became victorious and then formed the Asante nation making Kumasi its capital. Due to the relevant and critical roles that the Chiefs of Kumasi and Juaben played, the Kumasi Chief(Asantehene) was made the head of Asante Union while the Juaben Chief was also made the head of the Oyoko State within the Union(Oyokohene).

The Dwabenhene brought a number of gold items from the war and some of these items include the gold bangle which the Denkyirahene was wearing on his arm, the golden *oware* game the Denkyirahene was playing and a large amount of gold dust.

The Asantehene insisted that the Dwabenhene should bring the golden *oware* game so that it can be added to the head of Ntim Gyakari but Dwabenhene refused and this led to a misunderstanding which generated into a war.

In October, 1875, the untiring disputes between Kumasi and Dwaben took an intense turn when Mensa Bonsu who had replaced Kofi Karikari as Asantehene attacked Dwaben and her associates namely, Effiduase, Asokore and Oyoko. The factors that led to this very war was intricate than the first one which was just a clash of personalities.

According to Addo-Fening (1973) the causes of the second war between Dwaben and Kumasi were internal dynamics of the Dwaben State itself, growing rivalry among the two States and the external factor of direct British intervention in Kumasi- Dwaben affairs. In view of this, the people of New Juaben migrated from their traditional home in Asante Dwaben in the 1870s to settle at Akyem Abuakwa in the then British Protectorate of the Gold Coast.

The reason was that their leader Nana Kwasi Boateng was in exile at Kyebi in the 1830s and due to the generosity that the Akyems showed to him, his people decided to join him. For this reason, Nana Asafo Agyei of Juaben had no option but to migrate to Akyem Abukwa with his allies, stools and other paraphernalia.

Addo-Fening (1973) maintains that Nana Asafo Agyei and his compatriots, Yaw Omani, Chief of Effiduase and Anka Akyeamfuor Chief of Asokore travelled to Cape Coast to petition the British Government for ammunitions to continue the war against Asante but this was declined, then a number of the migrants became squatters and settled on the land around present day Koforidua.

So in March 1877, the British Government petitioned the Adontenhene of Akyem Abuakwa, Nana Ampao for land to settle the Dwabens in Kukurantumi and its environs. Nana Asafo Boateng did not like the idea of resettling his people in the Kukurantumi forest and so he repelled the government effort and this led to his detention in Elmina castle on 4th August, 1877 and then later exiled to Lagos. Whiles Nana Asafo Boateng was in Nigeria, he planned with Yaw Omani chief of Effiduase and Anka Akyeamfuor chief of Asokore who were exiled that they should rekindle the war between Dwaben and Kumasi but the chiefs did not succeed. In view of this, in February, 1878, the Dwaben Chiefs informed the then Governor called Freeling that they want to settle on the land which was arranged for them earlier.

Governor Freeling agreed and then asked them to go for the land and so within few weeks, the Dwaben Chiefs arrived at the current site of Koforidua to lay the foundation of the new state which is known as New Juaben. The New Juaben towns according to Addo-Fening (1973) were considered as extensions of the migrants' hometowns in Asante.

For that reason, those from Effiduase, Asokore and Oyoko named their towns after their old towns in Asante and those from Dwaben named their town Koforidua, Ada, Akwadum, Jumapo and Suhyen. Some of the migrants did not join their relatives at Koforidua but they established their own communities around Akyem Abuakwa and these settlements are Kankan(Sekyere), Nyirensi, Abekoase and Akadewaso. Yaw Omane and Anka Akyeamfuor who were chiefs of Effiduase and Asokore respectively were sent back home from exile in May, 1879, fifteen months after the foundation of the New Juaben was laid.

According to Nana Daasebre Prof.(Emeritus) Oti Boateng, the idea of celebrating Akwantukese festival came about as result of a dream he had after an Akwasidae ceremony and so five years after his enstoolment, he instituted the *Akwantukese* festival in 1997 in commemoration of their migration from Asante Dwaben.

The festival was named "*Akwantukese*"(great journey) due to the difficulties and problems that the people passed through when coming to New Juaben. The festival is aimed at bringing unity among the New Juabens and also projecting the historic and cultural heritage of the people, as well as to strengthen the unity between New Juaben and Old Dwaben.

2.0 Methodology

The study was conducted in Koforidua in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Koforidua is the Centre of New Juaben traditional area and the people are abreast with the Akan traditions and have a great festival known as *Akwantukese* which is proudly celebrated every year. This motivated the researcher to select the area for the study.

The study was driven by qualitative research approach. This research approach answers questions about the complex nature of phenomena, often with the purpose of describing and understanding

the phenomena from the participant's point of view. It also enabled the researcher to acquire an in depth knowledge about the educational values of the *Akwantukese* festival celebrations (Terrell, 2016). Descriptive study and case study were the main research methods that guided the researcher to accomplish the study. Descriptive research aided the researcher to give a vivid summary of everyday occurrences or specific event which was performed or organized by the people (Lambert and Lambert, 2012). The case study was employed to help understand situations or an events that occur to a particular person or a group at a particular point in time (Terrell, 2016 & Yin, 2013). The research instruments that assisted in the gathering of relevant data for the study were interviews and observations. In-depth personal interviews were conducted with the chiefs, sub-chiefs and queen mothers. The elderly persons and the youth were also engaged in focus group discussions where their experiences regarding the educational values of the festivals celebration were solicited for. As a non-participant observer, the researcher was able to record the events and the phenomena under study without any distractions (Kumekpor, 2002).

The purposive sampling techniques was employed to select the sample size of 50 which comprise of 5 chiefs, 4 sub-chiefs, 3 queen mothers, 15 elderly men and women and 22 youth who have witnessed the festival for the past five years or above. These people were selected based on the in depth knowledge that they have about the festival celebration. According to Creswell (2012) and Sandelowki (2000) purposive sampling is appropriate in a study of this nature because it helped the researcher to obtain the needed information for the study.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Educational Values associated with *Akwantukese* festival celebration

The study revealed that *Akwantukese* festival celebration is characterized with numerous educational values. It was observed that these values are seen in the activities and the various art

forms that feature in the celebration. These activities and the art forms directly or indirectly educate the people of the New Juaben and the general public in the course of *Akwantukese* festival celebration. In confirming this, Edinyang (2016) mentioned that the individual learns from his/her immediate environment through observation. This helps the individual to acquire values such as respect, patriotism, unity and love which help them to assume certain responsibilities. Edinyang further specified that festival celebration is a social activity through which a society gets its traditions, morals, customs, laws and values from. The research brought to the fore that the people of New Juaben cherish their cultural values and so certain activities were put in place to pass on these accumulated knowledges.

Below are the various cultural values that the *Akwantukese* festival celebration educates;

4.1 Virtue

Virtue which is one of the educational values the festival exhibits, plays a key role in the life of every individual. In view of this, a special day is set aside purposely to educate the members of the community mostly the teenagers and the youth on how they will think and do what is right, good and accepted by the community. At this set day which is usually Friday, the queen mother, sub-chiefs, the elderly persons and the community members meet at the Omanhene's palace. At the palace, some activities such as how to talk to elderly persons in the society, the way they should dress, how they should greet and how to refrain from pre-marital sex and pregnancy before marriage are taught. As witnessed by the research, the community members were taught to put their hands at their back when talking to elders. They were also taught how to use polite words and bringing their voices at a low tone when interacting with elders. In the course of this the members of the community especially the teenagers and the youth learn the accepted virtue of the society.

4.2 Unity

Unity is one of the pivotal values that *Akwantukese* festival celebration teaches. During the festival celebration, people from all walks of life come together to learn customs, dances and make merry. These activities bring unity and cordial relationship among community members and the visitors who attend the festival. Furthermore, elders and family heads settle disputes among family members who are not in good terms. This helps the general public to live in unity with people. learn how to live in unity with people. One of the respondents stated:

I am glad that I have been attending this festival every year because it has helped in solving the numerous conflict which was going on in my family house. I think if all the community members attend the festival, it will help them learn how to live in unity and harmony with people (Personal Communication, July, 10th 2019). Also, members from the various communities coming together to do general cleaning strengthens the ties and bond between them as well as promoting cordial relationships in homes, workplaces and the community as a whole. In supporting this, Hilbers (2006) and Falassi (1987) assert that festivals give community members the opportunity to unite, build up ties, promote affable relationships and express their culture. Football matches and indoor games such as ludo, *oware*, tag of peace and other activities are organized during the festival celebration among all the eight communities. It can be deduced that the games are organized to ensure unity and healthy relationship amongst all the people in the area. Through this activity, the community members learn to do things together as one people. In the same way, Cudny (2016), Gbedegbe (2013) and Akintan (2013) stated that festival celebration brings unity among the people of a community and also teaches them the traditional values.

4.3 Humility

Another important value that people acquire in the course of Akwantukese festival celebration is humility. Humility means self-effacement, unpretentiousness, humbleness, meekness and unassuming nature. A person is said to be humble when he or she respects authorities, down to earth, very docile and gentle. The people who attend or participate in Akwantukese festival celebration attain this value. This could be seen when the *Omanhene* (paramount) and his entourage are coming to the festival ground. All people present stand up for him and his people go round and greet the whole gathering and sit down before everybody sits. More so, the men who greet the *Omanhene* lower their clothes and also remove their slippers while the women also bend down and squat when greeting him. Also, the young and old spread their cloths on the floor for chiefs and queen mothers to walk on them during the festival celebration.

4.4 Love

Love is another relevant values that Akwantukese festival celebration impacts. Interviews and observations revealed that the queen mothers and the elderly women prepare food for visitors and

community members who are willing to eat. It was found that the queen mothers also gather themselves and visit hospitals and prisons to give them food and clothing. At times, they also organize health screening for the general public to show their love. This enable the youth and the young ones to learn to show love and affection to people that they meet.

4.5 Propriety

Participants and observers of *Akwantukese* festival celebration acquire propriety as a value. Propriety means decorum, modesty, decency, politeness, respectability and good manners. Considering the meaning of propriety, it could be stated that it is the good behaviour or character which is accepted in the New Juaben traditional area. Interviews conducted revealed that the young ladies who are selected for beauty contest during *Akwantukese* festival celebration are confined for about three days and taught how to be faithful to their future husbands. More so, they are not to use vulgar words when talking to people, dress decently and should try to maintain even temper when provoked and to respect the elderly people. In fact, these things that the ladies learn will help them to behave well in the communities in which they live.

4.6 Gratitude

The people of New Juaben always show appreciation and gratitude in the course of *Akwantukese* festival celebration. Gratitude is the act of showing appreciation or being grateful to someone who has done something good for somebody. As indicated earlier on, during the festival celebration, the *Omanehene* and selected chiefs go to all the rivers within the New Juaben to offer libation to the river deities for the support that they have given them. Also, they go to the *Obuotabiri* mountain where the shine is located to perform some rituals to thank the gods for protecting the people of New Juaben throughout the whole year. In addition, a special song is sung during the grand durbar(climax) to praise and thank the *Okyehene* and his people for giving the people of New Juaben some land to settle on. Chiefs and dignitaries from different places who attended the festival are also thanked for their support. Again, as indicated earlier, some chiefs and community members who lead exemplary lives and serve whole heartedly are thanked and awarded. The youth and the people who observe these activities get to know that one needs to be appreciative and thankful to any worthwhile thing that he or she receives from somebody.

4.7 Respectful

Respect is a value which is cherished in the New Juaben traditional area and for that matter, it is seen in every aspect of their daily life of which *Akwantukese* festival celebration is part. Respect is being courteous, polite, humble and dutiful. During the festival celebration, people exhibit a lot of behaviours which indicate that they respect authorities. For example, the way the young men who attend *Akwantukese* festival celebration remove their cloths to the chest level when greeting the *Omanhene* and other chiefs indicate the respect they accord them. Also, women curtsying down when greeting chiefs and their elders show the respect that the people of New Juaben have for their leaders. Furthermore, the way and manner people attach seriousness to the ban on noise making in the New Juaben traditional area indicate the kind of respect they have for the gods and ancestors. It was observed that when it gets to about 6 pm, the whole vicinity looks like a cemetery and no one will make noise. In addition, when chiefs are processing to the festival grounds, the sub-chiefs take the lead, then other chiefs follow before the *Omanhene* comes. Thus it is strictly done according to statuses. Also, when the *Omanhene* is coming to the durbar grounds, all the chiefs and sub-chiefs rise up for him to sit before they sit and this is a sign of respect that the attendees, community members and the general public learn from *Akwantukese* festival celebration. It can be concluded that the festival celebration enables the inhabitants and visitors to also learn to respect chiefs, elders and the rules and regulations in their communities. In affirming this, Tuijl and Berg (2016) and Cudny (2016) opine that festivals are occasions where people learn to acquire values such as respect, humility, unity and reverence. Other values which are in line with respect in the New Juaben traditional area are appreciation, honouring and venerating of the gods and their ancestors.

4.8 Loyalty

Loyalty is also one of the values learnt during *Akwantukese* festival celebration and it is characterized by trustworthiness, faithfulness, devotion, reliability and dependability. Loyalty is seen as the emotion or commitment that people attach to *Akwantukese* festival celebration. There is loyalty from the beginning of the festival to the end. For instance, the chiefs and elders who teach the newly enstooled chiefs and queen mothers traditions and customs as mentioned earlier on during festival devote their time to teach them. It was observed that the chiefs taught incessantly

for eight hours. When it was time for them to break and go for lunch they did not stop because of the commitment they had. More so, the way the chiefs involved themselves in the clean-up exercises such as weeding and cleaning of the gutters showed how committed they were. In addition, time taken to mend the drums, cloths and umbrellas indicated the elders were loyal and dedicated. All the aforementioned circumstances educate the people of New Juaben to also become loyal in the society in which they live in. From the above discussion, it could be affirmed that *Akwantukese* festival celebration brings people from all walks of life together and educate them on how to be loyal and dedicated. Likewise, Lee, Arcodia and Lee (2012) claim that festivals are able to draw people's attention and inculcate or instill good morals values such as reliability, honesty and loyalty in them.

4.9 Bravery / Courageousness

Akwantukese is one of the festivals celebrated in Ghana to inculcate a value such as bravery/courageous in community members of the New Juaben traditional area. Bravery which can also be called fortitude or courageousness is said to be the ability to be courageous, valor, bold, fearless, intrepid and dauntless. Likewise, Rate (2007) Cavanagh and Moberg (1999) are of the view that bravery is the capability to withstand what is necessary to achieve a good end, even in the face of great. As mentioned earlier on, it was found that the *Omanhene* and selected chiefs go to the *Obourtabiri* mountain to perform some rituals during the festival celebration. Information gathered revealed that this mountain is so high that if someone is not brave, fearless and courageous he cannot climb it. One respondent had this to say "although the mountain is very high and steep those of us who are bold and brave manage to climb and perform all the necessary rituals before we come down"

Again, it was observed that at the durbar grounds, the *abrafoɔ* fired gun shots at where the chiefs and traditional priest and priestess are sitting but they were all clam without moving. This can help onlookers and the people around learn to become courageous and brave in whatever problem they encounter.

4.10 Confidence

Attendees and inhabitants of the New Juaben traditional area acquire confidence as a value during the festival celebration. It was observed that in the course of the festival celebration, selected students from all Senior High Schools in the New Juaben participate in a quiz competition based on the history of the area. These students sit in front of a large crowd and then answer questions they have been asked. Once more, some children from the basic schools in the area also recite poems and perform drama for the general public to witness during the festival celebration. When this happens, students and other children who attend the festival also learn from their friends and try to be confident in whatever they do. Also the elderly and visitors who attend the festival will be encouraged to learn from the children and become confident.

4.11 Diligence

Diligence is a value which is characterized by assiduousness, meticulousness, conscientiousness, industriousness and attentiveness. Looking at *Akwantukese* festival celebration, traits of diligence is seen from the beginning to the end of the celebration. For instance, during the festival celebration, some people go to the *Omanhene's* palace to do thorough general cleaning and also mend all the tattered clothes, drums and umbrellas. These people use their strength and time to do the work properly and perfectly. One Opanin Kwaku Asante had this to say “if you are not hardworking and dedicated, you will not be called to come to the palace to work and so it becomes a competition for those of us who go there. Even if it is time for us to break and rest, we do not do it (personal communication 2018, 18th June). The aforementioned instance can let individuals who participate in *Akwantukese* festival celebration learn to be diligent and devoted in their lives.

4.12 Endurance/Patience

Endurance or patience is the value of fortitude, forbearance, self-control and serenity therefore endurance or patience simply means the ability to contain or tolerate something for a period of time. The people who attend *Akwantukese* festival celebration acquire the value of endurance or patience. Health screening always go on during the festival celebration for all the eight communities that comprise of the New Juaben traditional area. The health personnel who do the screening for the various communities normally screen the old men and women first before they

take care of the youth and younger ones but the people will not say anything and wait patiently till it gets to their turn. It was observed that the youth and the younger one go to the screening centre early but the nurses and doctors make sure that they attend to the elderly first but the youth understands and wait. This helps the youth and the general public learn to be patient and tolerant.

4.13 Generosity/ Kindness

The people of New Juaben associate generosity/kindness with benevolence, kindhearted and giving things out freely to a needy. Some people in the New Juaben show their love to visitors and even people who come from the place but do not stay there. A lot of people attend *Akwantukese* festival celebration and so accommodation becomes a problem at times but some people in the area volunteer and give their houses to these visitors free without collecting money. Some also give out their hotels and again feed the visitors for the number of days that they will spend. More so, some individuals also give monies out during fund raising for the development of the area. The aforesaid activities of individuals and some community members will encourage the youth and all the people in the area to also learn to be generous and kind to everybody.

4.14 Obedience

Another value which is highly recognized in the New Juaben traditional area is obedience. In course of *Akwantukese* festival celebration, some activities go on and these activities can help the people of the area to learn to become obedient. To begin with, the people in the area are not allowed to go to farm on some days and they obey it. Besides, when chiefs and elders are going to “*baamu*” (where chiefs are buried), women are not allowed to be there not even the queen mother. Also, women are not allowed to go to river Suhyenso and *Obourtabiri* shrine during the festival celebration because the place is sacrosanct. The women obey and do not do what they have been asked not to do. This helps the people of the area specially women and girl to submit themselves to the authorities and learn to obedient.

4.15 Religious

The people of New Juaben value Religiousness and for that matter expect all community members to be spiritual, sacred, devout, pious and holy. As indicated earlier on in the discussion of

Akwantukese festival celebration, church service is organized for the chiefs and all the people of New Juaben all the on the last Sunday of the festival celebration to thank the Almighty God for helping them to bring the festival celebration to a successful end. It was observed that the pastor prayed for the *Omanhene*, all chiefs and community members. Aside the church activities, libation were also offered to the gods and the ancestors. These activities will enable the youth and the general public learn to acknowledge the Supreme Being, ancestors and the gods and then worship them.

4.16 Cordiality

Akwantukese festival celebration transmits the value of cordiality between attendees' and people of New Juaben. Cordiality is associated with pleasantness, geniality, affability, friendliness, affectionateness, warmth and conviviality. During the festival celebration, people from other parts of the country and even outside the country attend and this brings a cordial relationship between the indigenes and the visitor. For instance, it was observed that during the festival celebration the people from the New Juaben and those from the North and Volta Regions danced together when they were playing the Dagomba music. Besides, the attendees from all walks of life and community members come together during the dinner organized by the *Omanhene*. These people eat, drink and socialize which lead to cordiality. This will enable the younger ones who attend *Akwantukese* festival learn to associate themselves very well with the people they meet.

4.17 Patriotic

Patriotism is one of the values that is exhibited during *Akwantukese* festival celebration. This value is characterized by nationalism, loyalty, jingoism and devotion. During the festival celebration, the people of New Juaben dedicate themselves to all the activities that go on in the celebration. For instance, during general cleaning exercise, all the community members participate fully and this helps the individual to feel that he or she is part of the society. Also, when the chiefs and elders are going to *Obourtabiri* to perform the rites, the youth carry the items and follow them to some point before they get back. This will help the people of New Juaben especially the young ones to learn involve themselves in all the activities that go on in the traditional area.

4.18 Discipline

Discipline is highly valued in the New Juaben traditional area and it is characterized by self-control, restraint and will power. Discipline is necessary in man's life and without it, one cannot succeed in life. It is seen as the act of teaching a person to follow the rules and regulations in the society in which he or she lives. During *Akwantukese* festival celebration, the people of New Juaben go by all the rules and regulations associated to the festival celebration. For instance, the people are asked not to make noise for a period of time, they also not to go river suhyen on some days and also to learn how to put on the traditional cloth. "We train or groom the younger ones in the various communities so that when we are dead and gone, they would be disciplined, get self-control and behave well in the societies in which they live" (Obaa Panin Afia Boahenmaa 2018, personal communication, 10th June). In supporting this, Mehta (2016) says that the mind and character of a person is trained for him to become disciplined so that he can fit properly into the society in which he lives to bring peace.

4.2.19 Cleanliness

Another value that the people of New Juaben cherishes is cleanliness and it is allied with purity, hygiene, sanitation and spotlessness. As mentioned earlier on, during *Akwantukese* festival celebration, the chiefs and the people of New Juaben clear the paths leading to all the rivers sides in the area. Again, a general cleaning is also done in all the communities to make the place look neat and attractive. This will help the youth and the younger one in the area to learn to keep personal hygiene and also live in clean environment.

4.2.20 Punctuality

Punctuality is one of the values that attendees and the general public can acquire when they participate in *Akwantukese* festival celebration. Punctuality basically means being prompt to a programme or being regular at a particular place on time. The observation made during *Akwantukese* festival celebration revealed that all the activities stipulated in the festival were done on time. For instance, all the people were asked to assemble at 8.30am during the health screening and about 85% of the community members were there around 7.00am. Besides the time for the beauty contest was 7.00pm but around 6.00pm the place was full. The newly enstooled chiefs and

queen mothers who were to go to *Omanhene's* palace at 10.00am to learn the traditions and the culture of the New Juaben got there as early as 8.00am. All the aforementioned scenarios indicate that the people of New Juaben value punctuality and for that matter they always try to be punctual to whatever activity that are asked to do. In view of this, the people who take part in the festival celebration will learn to be punctual or prompt to any programme that they are to attend in future because it can help them to develop their lives.

In the same vein, the art forms that are seen during *Akwantukese* festival also have aesthetic values and also express the culture and the life of the people of the New Juaben Traditional area.

Conclusion

This research aimed at drawing attention to the educational values *Akwantukese* festival celebration exhibits. The conclusions drawn from the study are positive and endorsed the *Akwantukese* festival celebration as a doable platform for exhibiting and sustaining the educational values of the society. The study showed that there is educational value in almost every activity that took place in the course of the festival celebration. For instance, the way sub-chiefs bend down, bring down their clothes and remove their headgear when greetings the *Omanhene* (paramount chief) is a sign of respect and the younger ones in the area also learn. Also the set aside day for educating members of the community helps to present and transfer the good part of the culture and tradition to the younger generation. Moreover, generosity, kindness and love are automatically exhibited and learnt by the young ones since natives willingly give their rooms freely for visitors to sleep without collecting money. The study recommends that the chiefs and the people of New Juaben should try as much as possible to celebrate *Akwantukese* festival every year because it educates the general public socially, psychologically and artistically. The young ones should be allowed by parents and guardians to fully participate in the festival celebration in order to learn the customs, traditions and the values of the land.

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